

LEARNING STYLES OF EFL STUDENTS IN ONLINE AND TRADITIONAL LEARNING ENVIRONMENTS

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Abstract: This article is devoted to the role and importance of learning styles of English as a foreign language students in both online and distance learning environments

Key words: EFL, distance learning, offline learning, learning styles, personal benefits, professional advantages.

Introduction: In the teaching-learning process, interaction among students and teachers plays crucial role. And what is interaction itself? Interaction is used to indicate the language which is used to maintain a conversation in the classroom and how learners are engaged both in improving their communicative abilities through collaboration and negotiation with others. Furthermore, it means that how they can use effective communication with each other in one place together.

Methods of analyses: The key factor of the teaching-learning process is not only determined by how the teachers teach but also, most importantly and principally is determined by how the students learn.

The students have differences learning styles when they listened to the explanation from the lecturers. Some gained their comprehension by doing group discussion or simply listened to tape recording and listened to direct explanation from the lecturers while some of them understand the subject visually when the lecturers trying to describe something by using video or presentation slides. The students made

up of various learning styles and it is always necessary for the lecturers, particularly the language lecturers to identify, respect and work on the diversity of the learners' differences.

Language learning styles as one of the main factors that help to identify how the students learn English as a foreign language with special emphasis on the role and significance of learning styles as one of the most influential techniques used during learning and teaching processes which will especially assist the teachers in getting to know the group of students in front of them and pave the way for them to go an extra mile. Therefore in a successful teaching-learning process the teachers not only used a good technique to convey the subject but also need help from the students to understand the subject with their way of learning such as how they understand the explanation from the teacher in the learning process itself.

Experts assert that individuals enjoy various learning styles. Learning styles make an important component in the learning environment. Students differ from each other in the way they learn as each student has his or her own strength and unique intelligence, and where possible individual needs should be taken into account in the teaching process. It is important to study learning styles because recent studies have shown that a match between teaching and learning styles helps to motivate students process of learning. Language learning styles are among the main factors that help determine how – and how well – students learn a foreign or second language.

Learning style is sometimes defined as the characteristic cognitive, affective, social, and physiological behaviors that serve as relatively stable indicators of how learners perceive, interact with, and respond to the learning environment.

Types of Learning Styles: One of the popular researchers emphasizing sensory modes is Reid (1987). She focuses on 'perceptual' and 'sociological' learning style preferences. Further, she developed her model and presented it in a questionnaire called Perceptual Learning Style Preference Questionnaire. She divides her learning style instrument into six categories to address visual, auditory, kinesthetic, tactile, as well as group and individual learning.

(1) Visual Major Learning Style Preference. They learn well from seeing words in books, on the chalkboard, and in workbooks. They remember and understand information and instructions better if they read them. They do not need as much oral explanation as an auditory learner, and they can often learn alone.

(2) Auditory Major Learning Style Preference. They learn from hearing words spoken and from oral explanation. They may remember information by reading aloud or by moving their lips as they read, especially when they are learning new material. They benefit from hearing audiotapes, lectures, and class discussions. They benefit

from making tapes to listen to, by teaching other students, and by conversing with their teacher.

(3) Kinesthetic Major Learning Style Preference. They learn best by experience, by being involved physically in classroom experiences. They remember information well when they actively participate in activities, field trips, and role-playing in the classroom.

(4) Tactile Major Learning Style Preference. They learn best when they have the opportunity to do “hands-on” experiences with new materials. That is, working on experiments in a laboratory, handling, and building models, and touching and working with new materials provide them with the most successful learning situations.

(5) Group Major Learning Style Preference. They learn more easily when they study with at least one other student, and they will be more successful in completing work well when they work with others. They value group interaction and classwork with other students, and they remember information better when they work with two or three classmates.

(6) Individual Major Learning Style Preference. They learn best when they work alone. They think well when they study alone, and they remember the information they learn by themselves. They understand material best when they learn it alone, and they make better progress in learning when they work by themselves

A foreign language is a language studied in an environment where it is not the primary vehicle for daily interaction and where input in that language is restricted. The optimum learning achievement will be gained when the various differences students like habit, interest, learning style are accommodated by lecturer in choosing methods, materials, which appropriate with students' learning style. The quality of teaching and learning process at University can be improved when the lecturer understand and consider the characteristics and learning of the students in choosing methods, techniques of teaching, teaching materials which are suitable with the varieties of students learning styles. When the students learning styles are suitable with the teachers' teaching styles, there will be more positive things can be gained, such as enjoyable learning atmosphere, students' motivation and interest are increased. However if the teachers' teaching styles and the students' learning styles do not match each other, it will cause disappointment and frustration for both sides.

Literature analysis: Learning styles have been defined in multiple ways, depending upon one's perspective. Learning style has been defined by various scholars mostly as a signal for individual differences. These differences may manifest itself in 'life styles' and even in personality types. Learning style is an approach used by the students in learning a new language or other subjects. learning styles as “a profile of

the individual's approach to learning, a blueprint of the habitual or preferred way the individual perceives, interacts with and responds to the learning environment". Furthermore, learning styles are defined by Dörnyei as "a profile of the individual's approach to learning, a blueprint of the habitual or preferred way the individual perceives, interacts with and responds to the learning environment".

Values also play a crucial role to identify learning styles, learning preferences and outcomes. The process of purposeful social practice, a person gives meaning to various objects and phenomena of the surrounding world, which, thanks to this, become values -means to achieve certain goals. Moreover, we are talking not only about pragmatic values, but also about ethical, aesthetic and other relations associated with the values of goodness, beauty, truth, since they are also necessary to achieve the corresponding goals of cultural activity. Thus, every phenomenon, every element of reality, transformed and mastered in human activity, becoming an element of a certain culture, acquires meaning and meaning for the social community and the individual associated with it, becomes a value. It seems that these three approaches develop different potentialities inherent in the initial understanding of value as an idea formed in the course of social practice about the significance of certain elements of the external and internal world for human life. In other words, the essence of value is the creative significance of the phenomena of the life world fixed in one way or another by a person. ⁵¹

We have to remark that understanding learning styles and the significance of learning styles in the teaching/learning process is a key factor in effective teaching as it was mentioned by Sarasin, "teaching cannot be successful without a knowledge of learning styles and a commitment to matching them with teaching styles and strategies"⁵². Therefore, increasing our comprehension about learning styles both in distance and face-to-face learning environments leads to a great number of positive and influential outcomes such as:

Personal benefits :

Develops self-image

Enables them to enjoy any learning process

Motivates greater curiosity and motivation for lifelong learning

⁵¹ Burkhanova Mamura Gulyamovna. (2022). AXIOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF STUDENT MORALITY. European Journal of Research Development and Sustainability, 3(2), 12-14. Retrieved from <https://scholarzest.com/index.php/ejrd/article/view/1795>

⁵² Karabuga, Ferhan. "Match or Mismatch Between Learning Styles of Prep-Class EFL Students and EFL Teachers." Electronic Journal of Foreign Language Teaching, Vol. 12, No. 2. 2015, pp. 276–288.

Shows both educators and learners how to take advantage of their natural skills ⁵³

Professional advantages :

Helps to improve cooperation among colleagues

Enables you to stay up-to-date professionally

Discussion and conclusion : We can not only reduce the stress and frustration of learning experiences, but also be able to expand our existing learning and studying strategies by enhancing our knowledge about learning styles of English learners as a foreign language. In addition to this, both in e-learning and traditional learning, EFL students learning styles play vital role since these learning styles enable students to succeed in school, college, university and also provide an opportunity of most effective educational techniques to score better on tests and exam. Consequently, it would be better whenever educators combine multiple learning styles together with the aim of making learning and teaching processes more vivid and interesting for every members of group.

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